
57. Technology preparation for Gaia

WHY DOES ESA FUND the development of space science missions? Why do some of these run over budget, and over schedule? Does the fact that both Hipparcos and Gaia were launched within a year of their target launch date indicate that they were simpler missions than some others in ESA's scientific portfolio?

LET ME START WITH MY FIRST question: why does ESA facilitate and fund the development of space science missions?

Amongst ESA directorates are satellite missions with a utilitarian function, notably those within the classes of Earth observation, of telecommunications, and of satellite navigation. Missions in the science directorate instead focus on scientific research: aiming to further our understanding of the Sun, our solar system, our Galaxy, and the Universe beyond. By advancing our knowledge, they sit at the heart of our culture.

At the same time, these scientific missions push the frontiers of technology, allowing more advanced experiments, and greater advances in scientific understanding than ever before. New missions proposed and accepted by ESA's scientific advisors must push these technical and scientific boundaries. If they are too modest in their technological vision, they will be of limited appeal to national industries. But if they are too unrealistic, problems may arise during their construction, and delays and cost overruns will follow.

WHY ARE NEW technological advances a requirement when selecting new missions? Several answers can be given. New scientific questions can frequently only be answered using more advanced experiments than available before. And these will generally demand an advance in the underlying technologies.

Industries embrace the opportunity for advances in their technological capabilities because this puts them at an advantage with respect to their competitors. And the link between advances in fundamental science and benefits to national economies has been widely demonstrated (see my essay on 'Gaia and GDP', #9).

THE REASONS FOR SPACE SCIENCE MISSIONS (and indeed for any large project whether in the public or private sector) running over budget and over schedule, can be many and complex.

As examples, the project may have been overly ambitious for the technologies available. This may in turn be traced to undue optimism of the originators, to understating the challenges in order to get the project accepted, or to insufficient rigour in the project evaluation, or to an underestimate of the resources required.

Projects are often subject to unrealistic 'requirement creep' as they are implemented, where new and more ambitious goals are introduced along the way. Delays can often be traced to errors in management, including a lack of progress monitoring, changes in specifications, inadequate resources, an absence of contingency planning, and many others.

CORRECTLY ANTICIPATING the challenges presented by new requirements in technologies has always been a challenge for space missions. In the early days of space science, a project may have been accepted with only limited attention having been given to the challenges in actually implementing it.

Different project 'phases' were introduced to help quantify the requisite steps. Both ESA and NASA, for example, have long followed the idea of a project phase A being dedicated to a sort of 'feasibility study' (i.e., does the project appear broadly feasible, given what we know about current and projected state-of-the-art in technology?), leading to the mission's acceptance (or otherwise), followed by a phase B dedicated to a detailed system design. This in turn would be followed by the satellite construction and testing (phases C/D), followed by launch and operations (phases E/F).

Durations vary, but are (indicatively) around 2 years for phase B, and around 6–8 years for phase C/D. The feasibility study phase can vary more widely, anything from 2–5 years up to one or two decades or more in the case of extremely demanding technologies such as for the ESA–NASA gravitational wave mission, LISA.

RELATIVELY SMALL INDUSTRIAL teams are typical during phases A–B, perhaps involving some 2–3 industries and some 50–100 people. Costs escalate during the implementation phases C/D, when tens of companies, and some thousands of people, might be involved.

Consequently, unexpected problems encountered during phase B may have significant schedule but relatively small financial consequences, while major technological problems encountered in the implementation phase, where costs of hundreds of the associated work force might be carried along, can be substantial.

OVER THE PAST DECADE OR SO, procedures have been developed in an attempt to control these costs and schedule risks. For example, ESA today follows the approach of ‘approving’ a project once the scientific objectives have been endorsed and once the required technology development activities have been identified, but only finally ‘adopting’ the project once the technology development has reached a specified level of maturity.

Quantifying the technological maturity of each satellite component today follows a strict hierarchical ‘Technology Readiness Level’, where each hardware item is classified from level TRL1 (the basic principles have been reported), through TRL4 (the item has been validated in a laboratory environment), TRL6 (in which a prototype has been verified in the relevant environment), all the way up to TRL9 (in which the system has been ‘flight proven’ through successful mission operations). Today, ESA requires that the mission must be based on technology that can credibly achieve TRL6 by the time of the mission’s *adoption*.

ACHIEVING OR demonstrating these TRLs is an interesting problem in its own right. As an example, Surrey Satellite Technology Ltd (SSTL) have employed the approach of operating satellites with a certain ‘flight proven’ technology serving some specific purpose (for example, attitude control), such that the mission can be largely guaranteed to function, while carrying a redundant but more innovative back-up technology to carry out the same task by way of a technology demonstrator.

As a specific example of a real schedule for an ongoing (but particularly challenging) mission, the first concept for a gravitational wave detection mission was proposed in the US in 1985, and to ESA in 1993 in response to the Call for Mission Proposals for the third ‘medium size mission’ (M3) within ESA’s ‘Horizon 2000’ programme. It subsequently appeared as the fourth ‘cornerstone mission’ in Horizon 2000+ in 1995.

Required technologies satisfying the TRL classification system were identified in an ESA–NASA study which I chaired between 2014–16. The study report detailed a development schedule constrained to an ESA Science Programme Committee adoption in early 2025, and a launch in 2034.

GAIA STARTED OUT, in 1993, as a conceptual sketch on a piece of paper, further refined through discussions with the ESA technical directorate and, later, industry engineers.

Working closely with the appointed ESA Study Manager, Oscar Pace (who had led the Assembly, Integration, and Testing group within the ESA project team for Hipparcos) we then progressively finalised a conceptual design, and outline technological development plan.

Seven years later, as a result of a 2-year study involving our scientific and industrial study teams, and leading to the 360-page Concept and Technology Study Report (ESA–SCI(2000)4) presented to ESA’s advisory groups in 2000, we had identified the various development activities needed to place the developments for Gaia on a secure technological footing. In the Executive Summary, these were listed as:

- high-performance, small-pixel (9 μm) CCDs
- high integration, low-noise detector chain
- SiC technology validation for mirrors and structure
- high data rate phased array antenna for an L2 orbit
- database/processing architecture for 20 TB of data

In more detail, identified development was foreseen for:

- three-side buttable, small pixel, high-performance CCDs for the astrometric instruments;
- large-area, highly integrated CCD-based focal plane assembly for the astrometric instruments;
- large size, high-performance CCDs for the spectrometer;
- large size, high-performance CCD for the photometer;
- highly integrated, high-speed, low-noise detection chains for the astrometric focal planes (including design, bread-boarding, and development of ASIC hybrids);
- large area SiC mirrors (manufacturing and testing);
- ultra-stable large size SiC structure and application to the payload primary structure;
- large size deployable solar array sunshield assembly;
- phased array antenna for high data rates and L2 orbits;
- complementary qualification of a FEOP based reaction control subsystem (delta-qualification for the adequate range of thrust and lifetime);
- optimised on-board data compression algorithm;
- payload data handling electronics architecture;
- ground verification calibration and required facilities;
- inch-worm actuators for the refocusing mechanism;
- data base architecture, including storage, archive and processing of the satellite data.

THE STUDY REPORT argued that the advanced technology programme could be completed in 2003, with phase B completed in mid-2005, all leading to a possible launch in 2009. When the mission was later accepted by ESA’s advisory committees in 2000, and following the assignment of Bepi-Colombo as cornerstone 5, with Gaia as cornerstone 6, the target launch date was 2012.

These technology development activities were followed, and the satellite duly launched in December 2013. Whilst therefore largely adhering to its target implementation schedule, Gaia remains one of ESA’s most advanced and complex satellite projects.